

Website

D13.2

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PU	Public	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
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About OneNet

OneNet will provide a seamless integration of all the actors in the electricity network across Europe to create the conditions for a synergistic operation that optimizes the overall energy system while creating an open and fair market structure.

The project OneNet (One Network for Europe) is funded through the EU's eighth Framework Programme Horizon 2020. It is titled "TSO – DSO Consumer: Large-scale demonstrations of innovative grid services through demand response, storage and small-scale (RES) generation" and responds to the call "Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future (LC)".

While the electrical grid is moving from being a fully centralized to a highly decentralized system, grid operators have to adapt to this changing environment and adjust their current business model to accommodate faster reactions and adaptive flexibility. This is an unprecedented challenge requiring an unprecedented solution. For this reason, the two major associations of grid operators in Europe, ENTSO-E and EDSO, have activated their members to put together a unique consortium.

OneNet will see the participation of a consortium of over 70 partners. Key partners in the consortium include: already mentioned ENTSO-E and EDSO, Elering, EDP Distribution, RWTH Aachen University, University of Comillas, VITO, European Dynamics, Ubitech, Engineering, and the EUI's Florence School of Regulation (Energy).

The key elements of the project are:

1. Definition of a common market design for Europe: this means standardized products and key parameters for grid services which aim at the coordination of all actors, from grid operators to customers;
2. Definition of a Common IT Architecture and Common IT Interfaces: this means not trying to create a single IT platform for all the products but enabling an open architecture of interactions among several platforms so that anybody can join any market across Europe; and
3. Large-scale demonstrators to implement and showcase the scalable solutions developed throughout the project. These demonstrators are organized in four clusters coming to include countries in every region of Europe and testing innovative use cases never validated before.

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1 Introduction

As part of task 13.1., Project identity and communication and dissemination strategy, the EUI as WP13 leader, in cooperation with the Project Coordinator (FhG) and with the contribution of all the project partners, created the project website. The project website was launched in M5 of the project and can be accessed at: <https://onenet-project.eu/>

The present document outlines the structure of the project website, as well as the parameters that will be used to monitor and measure the impact of this communication and dissemination tool.

2 Project Website Structure and Impact Monitoring

The website (<https://onenet-project.eu>) is structured in a way to provide:

- overall information about the project
- information about the project consortium
- access to project related publications
- the latest project related news and events
- blog posts
- option of subscribing to the newsletter
- a list of useful links
- information about GRIFOn
- a press room for media relations.

The WP13 leader will be responsible for monitoring accesses and preparing reports regarding the impact of the website as a communication and dissemination tool. The following parameters will be monitored:

- for the OneNet newsletter, information on subscriptions, open rates and click-through to the website will be provided after every send using the inbuilt analytics of Mailchimp, the email list manager used.
- for the website, we will monitor activity using Google Analytics and Google Search Console. We will report on:
 1. Monthly views by traffic sources, and how each one performs to identify strengths and weaknesses.
 2. The performance of the website, including details on browser, audience, growth and mobile vs desktop speed.
 3. Analysis of the content of the website, focusing on which pages attract the most views, and which pages have the highest 'bounce' rate (leave the site after only viewing one page).
 4. Which websites are referring traffic to our website so we can analyse how partnerships and social media are performing.
 5. Specific analysis of social media (how many users go through to the website to read content, what social actions they take).

New parameters may be added during the implementation of the project. To ensure maximum visibility to the website, we are using a Search Engine Optimisation application (Wordpress SEO by Yoast) to analyse the content of the site to fit into best practices. To improve 'page authority', i.e. how high a page ranks through search engine results, we will encourage all partners to create links to the project on their own institutional

websites. New proposals on ways to generate content that can attract visitors may be added during the implementation of the project.

Regarding the private area of the website: the project consortium uses a private Microsoft SharePoint managed by the Coordinator, to store and share official documents, templates, and deliverables related to each of the WPs. It is also a working area for all the project related documents.

3 Appendix

The screenshot displays the OneNet website layout. At the top right is the OneNet logo. Below it is a navigation bar with links for Home, The Project, News & Events, Publications, and GRIFOn. The main content area features a large banner for GRIFOn with a background image of wind turbines. The banner text reads: "GRIFOn (GRIFOnium) is a platform facilitating constant dialogue between the project and the stakeholders to define applicable solutions and create consensus at European level for a quick and efficient process of standardisation." Below this is a yellow "More about GRIFOn" button. Underneath the banner is a "News & Events" section with two featured articles: "Five things to know about OneNet Project" (dated February 14, 2021) and "Launching OneNet: One Network for Europe" (dated October 13, 2020). A dark blue footer contains a "Subscribe to newsletter" form with an email input field and a yellow "Subscribe" button. Below the footer is a "Key facts about the project" section with four icons and descriptions: Knowledge base, Demo clusters, European consortium, and GRIFOn. The bottom of the page features a "GRIFOn Join the community" banner with a yellow "More" button. The footer includes the OneNet logo, a list of links for "About OneNet" and "More info", the European Union flag, and a note about funding from the Horizon 2020 programme.

